

Classification of rectangles

"Classification of Quadrilaterals"

In many cases, students find it difficult to know what type (class) of a quadrilateral is, for example, a rhombus, or which quadrilateral represents both a rectangle and a parallelogram, etc. This caused disequilibrium among the students. I thought how to eliminate this deficiency. This prompted me to create a poster "Classification of Quadrilaterals".

The resource corresponds to the achievable results defined by the ESS, contributes to the development of semiotic competence, as well as the development of the ability to include categories. It helps me to reach the following achievable results defined by the ESS:

them.VII.9. The student can recognize geometric figures, compare and classify their types.
them. VIII.8. The student can use the properties of figures to classify figures and compare their types.

them.IX.10. The student can use the concept of "geometric locus of points" to depict objects and describe their properties.

them. X.9. The student can use the ways of representing geometric figures and formulating statements.

them.XII.5. The student can find/estimate the dimensions of figures or their elements and use them to solve practical problems.

The resource can be used in virtually all grades starting from grade VII, it is intended and useful for students of any academic level, with minor modifications or in the same form it can be used for lower grades as well.

Before introducing the resource to the students and before hanging the poster, I asked frontal questions in the classes: is a square a rhombus, is a square a parallelogram and a rectangle, etc. It must be said that many questions were answered, although there were gaps in the answers, which were immediately eliminated within a few seconds after the poster was shown.

It is logical that after the first use (acquaintance) it should be hung in a visible place, and if necessary, the teacher should gesture to the student to look at it.

The field of use of the resource can be defined as planimetry, it is possible to use it in stereometry lessons, when polygons and their intersections are discussed.

Let's take for example the VIII class, where the topic "quadrilaterals" is studied, I used the poster when I finished the topic completely. This encouraged the students very much, they all looked at the poster carefully and easily classified the figures

The use of the resource contributed to the development of semiotic competence, the development of the ability to include categories, as well as the development of the ability of metacognition.

There were no problems during the use of the resource. The use of the mentioned resource was also motivating for me and I was once again convinced that the teacher should constantly increase his knowledge, should be searching, creative, and all this has a positive effect on the teacher himself and also on the results of the students.

Using the resource is easy, in particular: the figure at the beginning of the directed section is at the same time the figure at the end of the section.

For example, a square is both a rhombus and a rectangle, which at the same time represent a parallelogram, etc. The resource is content-sound, organized and consistent, it is reusable, it promotes the involvement of students, increases the motivation of students, therefore it can be used by other mathematics teachers of the school, which will improve the learning process. It will make it fun and productive.

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20.09.2016